

PHOTONICS IN COHERENT MULTIBAND RADAR SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The cross-fertilization between photonics and microwave systems is setting new paradigms in radar systems leading towards a new generation of multifunctional systems, able to manage multiple simultaneous coherent radio signals at different frequencies, enabling multispectral imaging for advanced surveillance systems. This paper presents the first multiband photonics-based radar transceiver, reporting on the first demonstrator of fully coherent dual band radar.

Keywords: *Photonics, radar systems*

1. INTRODUCTION

Radar systems applications, traditionally limited to ranging and surveillance, are broadening towards new multifunctional and multiband sensing systems, requiring higher performance in terms of spatial and velocity resolution, and entailing the requirement of very stable radiofrequency (RF) sources, and very precise signal detection and digitization. The multifunctional radar systems also require reconfigurable and software-defined RF signal generators, capable of producing wideband waveforms over carriers ranging up to the millimeter waveband (MMW, above 30GHz), while maintaining the phase stability necessary for coherent pulse-Doppler processing, target imaging, and clutter rejection [1]. Furthermore, a radar receiver with the digital back-end working in the MMW range would be beneficial for the system reconfigurability and reliability, also reducing the noise with respect to the analog counterpart [2]. Nevertheless, nowadays the direct generation of modulated RF signals by means of direct digital synthesizers (DDSs) with acceptable stability is limited to few GHz, and the necessary process of multiple up-conversions worsens the generated signals phase noise [2]. Similarly, the precision of the analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) drops with increasing analog input bandwidth and sampling speed [3], thus requiring further down-conversion stages. Therefore, the technical requirements for software-defined radars are currently a serious challenge for the high-speed DDSs and ADCs. In the last decade, microwave photonics is being investigated in order to overcome several issues of electronic systems, including the radar limitations. In fact, microwave photonics aims

at exploiting the specific features of photonics, as wide bandwidth, immunity to electromagnetic interferences (EMI), low-loss and low-distortion propagation, low phase noise of optical clocks, and extremely high frequency flexibility. These attractive and unique properties are exploited for obtaining a wide range of functionalities. Photonics can be used for generating RF signals in a wide range of carrier frequencies (up to the MMW) with superior phase stability, also permitting the simultaneous generation of multiple RF carriers [4]-[5]. It allows controlling the beam formation of wideband signals in phased array antennas (PAAs) by true-time delays [6]-[7], avoiding beam squinting effects, with the capability for implementing a tunable filtering [8] or other signal elaborations. At the receive side, photonics-based analogue-to-digital conversion, [9]-[10] guarantees large input bandwidth, high sampling rates with extremely low time jitter, fully digital approach, independence to the RF carrier, and the capability to simultaneously receive multiple signals. Finally, the extensive use of photonics in a radar system allows easily distributing the RF signals from the transceiver to the antenna site (where the conversions to/from the electronic domain take place) through optical fibers, with low loss, low distortions, and EMI immunity.

2. PHOTONICS-BASED TRANSCEIVER

The conventional generation of RF signals is performed through multistage electronic up-conversions (Fig. 2 top), that exploit different electronic local oscillators with a stability that rapidly decreases as the RF gets higher. Each stage introduces non-negligible phase and amplitude noise due to the phase drifts of the local oscillator and the use of noisy electronic mixers. The photonic RF generation is based on the concept of heterodyning two lasers in a photodiode (Fig. 2 bottom), producing an RF signal whose frequency is equal to the detuning between the two lasers. This way, thanks to the wide opto-electric bandwidth of the available commercial photodiodes, generation of RF signals up to 100GHz is easily achievable. Moreover, if one of the lasers is modulated, the heterodyning operation transfers the modulation to the carrier frequency given by the lasers detuning. Since optical modulators are available with electro-optical bandwidth above 40GHz, photonics allows the generation of ultra-broad bandwidth RF signals up to the MMW. The phase stability of the generated RF signals depends on the reciprocal phase

behavior of the two beating optical lasers that must be locked in phase with each other, as in the case of mode-locked lasers (MLLs) (Fig. 2 bottom). These are pulsed lasers, whose optical spectrum is composed of several longitudinal modes at a detuning defined by the pulse rate.

Fig. 2. Conventional (top) and photonics-based (bottom) RF generation.

The conventional RF receiver (Fig. 3a) performs multiple electronic down-conversions to move the detected signals into the bandwidth of the ADCs. As in the case of the transmitter, each down-conversion stage introduces non-negligible phase and amplitude noise, which increase when detected frequency gets higher. The photonics-based RF detection exploits the huge electro-optical bandwidth of optical modulators to move the RF signals in the optical domain. Exploiting the concept of heterodyning, an optical RF down-conversion has been effectively implemented. By using the MLL, at the modulator input, it is possible to implement the optical down conversion of RF signals at any frequency [11]. In the scheme, reported in Fig. 3b, every comb laser is modulated by the RF signal, generating sidebands at f_{RF} from the carrier, that are detuned f_{IF} from the closest comb line. Therefore, detecting the entire spectrum by the photodiode, all the sidebands are coherently downconverted at f_{IF} and can be digitized by an electrical ADC.

Fig. 3. RF detection based on conventional electronic scheme (a), and on photonics downconversion (b) or sampling (c).

The use of the optical pulses from MLL has been also proposed to directly sample high frequency RF signals. In [12], as reported in Fig. 3c, the optical sampling occurs modulating the MLL pulses by the RF signal. The modulated pulses represent the optical samples and the sampling rate is given by the MLL repetition rate. In [12] we have exploited this detection technique in conjunction with a time-domain demultiplexing in a fast

optical switching matrix, in order to parallelize the samples to lower sample pulse trains that are synchronously digitized by electronic ADCs. In this way it is possible to achieve a RF signal sampling with a bandwidth higher than the one of the exploited electronic ADCs.

The microwave photonic functionalities described above can be combined to realize a complete photonics-based RF transceiver. A single MLL can conveniently serve as the optical source for both the transmitter and the receiver subsystems, reducing size, weight and costs of the overall photonics-based transceiver. In [11] we used a MLL with repetition rate $f_{rep}=400MHz$. The exploited RF generation scheme is slightly different from the one depicted in Fig. 2 (bottom), for overcoming few practical issues due to the use of discrete devices. The desired radar waveform is digitally generated at a low intermediate frequency (IF) and fed into the RF port of an electro-optical modulator to modulate the MLL output. This optical signal is then detected by a photodiode (PD). The beating products generated by the detection process in the PD generates a replica of the radar waveform for all the frequencies equal to $f_0=nf_{rep}+IF$. A filter at the PD output selects the proper signal replica to be transmitted. The results of the performance characterization of the transceiver are reported in [11]. The advantages of the photonic approach are evident in the extreme frequency flexibility over tens of GHz, and in the precision of the digitization for any input frequency. These features are fundamental for enabling the software-defined radio paradigm not only in future radars systems but also in the next generation of flexible wireless communication systems.

3. THE PHOTONICS-BASED RADAR

The coherent radar has been implemented both in single configuration (PHODIR), where a front-end in the X-band (9.9GHz) has been connected to the photonics-based transceiver [11], and in dual band configuration, implementing also an additional front-end in the S-band (2.7GHz) [14]. PHODIR has been first tested in several field trial experiments, with the aim of evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed photonic approach. A field trial run in collaboration with *GEM elettronica* in San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy has permitted to perform a direct comparison with a state-of-the-art commercial radar, in X-band. Fig. 7 (left) shows the detection trace taken by PHODIR with a rotating antenna. A small echo from a moving boat at a distance of about 0.42 nautical miles (NM) is investigated. Fig. 7 (right) depicts the range/velocity map of this target. The inset shows the range profile, which highlights a radar range resolution of the 3.75m, thanks to the employed chirped waveform (40MHz). Fig. 8 depicts the comparison between PHODIR (right) and the commercial radar systems. The graph shows different target detections within the maximum unambiguous

range (8NM). The minimum detectable signal (MDS) of PHODIR has been demonstrated to be comparable with the MDS of the commercial system that outperformed PHODIR, of 6 dB, mainly due to its higher processing gain. From an hardware point of view the performance of the two systems are similar. In addition the PHODIR transceiver offers other important features like bandwidth extension, frequency and waveform agility.

Fig. 7. PHODIR radar detection of the San Benedetto del Tronto harbour area (left). Range -Doppler map of the detected boat (right). Inset: range profile of the detected target.

Fig. 8. Comparison of a commercial radar (left) and of the photonic single band radar (right).

Afterwards, the system has been expanded with a second front-end for dual band functionalities [13], thus exploiting the signal coherence provided by photonics. In order to use the two separate bands, two radar signals are generated with different intermediate frequency IF_1 and IF_2 , and combined to modulate the MLL. After the photodetection, signals at frequency $f_1 = mf_{rep} \pm IF_1$ and $f_2 = nf_{rep} \pm IF_2$ are generated, with m and n independent integer numbers chosen to fall in the desired bands. An RF filter then selects the signal replica at the desired frequency. At the receiver, the echos are optically downconverted to the original IF s simultaneously.

The field trial has been carried out from the roof of our building exploiting the aerial traffic of the nearby Pisa airport. Fig. 9 reports the range/velocity map of an aerial target exploiting the X (fig. 9a) and S (fig. 9b) band respectively. A strong echo peak is visible at a distance of about 4.6km in both the S and X maps with a velocity of about 55m/sec corresponding to a Doppler frequency of about 1.1KHz and 3.7KHz for S and X band, respectively. This allows to have a higher velocity resolution with the higher RF. The range profile of the detected target is depicted in Fig.9c for the S band (dashed red curve) and the X band (dotted blue curve). The range resolution is almost the same for both bands. However, thanks to the band coherence, the data of the X

and S bands can be combined by data fusion algorithms in order to improve the range resolution. In fact, as can be seen from the black curve in the plot, the range resolution obtained with the merged data is about doubled with respect to a single frequency band. The 3dB width of the target peak is about 9m for the single channels and 5m for the fused data. As demonstrated by the field trial experiments the proposed dual band radar is capable of independently manage two different radar waveforms in two different frequency bands (S and X), thus allowing a multi frequency analysis of the scene under observation. Moreover, exploiting the same pulsed laser source for the generation of both S and X band signals, makes the two transmission bands phase locked, thus opening the way for advanced signal processing and data fusion techniques.

Fig. 9. Range velocity maps of the S-band (A) and X-band (B) and the range profiles (C) of the dual band radar.

4. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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